

Editorial

What is the Best Journal to Publish your Scholarly Article?

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E D I T O R I A L

Dear Readers,

I hope many of us are confused regarding selection of the best journal to get our scholar articles published. I am attempting to come out of the confusion through discussion with a panel of experts and scholars across the globe and special assistance from Srinivas University research scholars and professors. Actually, we have a WhatsApp group under the control of Prof Dr PS Aithal, Vice-Chancellor. The university has several experts like the research director and many more faculties along with scholars with advanced degrees among whom a common topic of discussion is where to submit articles for publication.

My External Supervisor of PhD, Late Prof Dr Kameshor Mishra, D Litt was a great academician who used to encourage me to write quality paper without any instruction on submission and during my post-doctorate as gateway of D.Sc. where I was lucky to have Prof Dr PS Aithal as my supervisor who suggested me to write paper which involves at least one message or innovation. Based on his suggestions, here is the minimum standard to submit a paper for publication.

- Open Access Journal with ISSN where Article should be freely Accessible to Readers
- Copyright should be with Authors. Only publication rights can be given to publishers
- No or zero Article Processing Charges (APC)
- Article should have DOI preferably CrossRef to fetch any citations to the published article
- Submitted Article should be reviewed for originality, novelty, scholarly format, plagiarism, grammar mistakes, citation-reference matching
- The published article should be available for Google Scholar search directly from the Journal immediately after publication

He advised us to go to current Issue (in its website) of the Journal for its suitability for publication. Copy the last published article title along with its authors name. Paste it into the "Google scholar search page" and if the paper is available for search and connects to its published

journal page, then only submit the Article. One of the scholars, Dr S Ramanathan, argued with evidence that many journals do not have ISSN also though they are accepted all over the world like Harvard Business Review, which has no ISSN also which encouraged Prof Aithal to support his argument by saying, "think from top, not from bottom." Only commercial journals who want to make profit should think about accreditation. Other Journals like Advanced Research Publications or Srinivas are free publication model like God created free air and water, need no accreditation. Further he added that Journal doesn't mean Indexing. And Indexing doesn't mean SCI or Scopus. There are many Journals included in UGC care and Scopus totally casual and profit-making one. In the meanwhile, I focused on citation without considering self-citation as UGC guideline does not allow self-citation on which Dr PK Paul consolidates saying self-citation is not bad when required. What matters the most is the innovative aspect of your research and its impact on the community. Researchers can look for your papers into for peer-reviewed, non-article processing charges, quality journals which follow ethical principles and try to limit the self-citation to the very minimal extent. Self-citation should not be misused to get onesown increased citation score. Quality of paper and citation of paper are not directly related. Since quality is intangible, by mistake citation is used to represent it. Citation shows continuation of research by your group or other groups. There is a famous scholarly paper published in 1997 as Open Access article in Famous Journal "NATURE" with title, "Self-trapping of Incoherent White Light" by Matthew Mitchell & Mordechai Segev. This paper has 80% citations of their own previously published papers because they are only pioneers in research of self-trapped incoherent soliton generation. Nature Journal never considered these citations as self-citations because they are relevant citations. When you know the objective of the citation, you will never worry about whether it is self or others. In scholarly articles, to avoid repetition and to continue the work of already published results, citation is used. For a real researcher, when writing the paper, only related papers/ results are important than who has published it. People who don't have any work will think about self-citation, mutual-citation, and others' citation. Citation is not for showing authors or his collaborators published papers. Citation is for showing related results to support the importance of your findings. You need not be bound by any rules while writing your article. In the process of peer/ editorial reviews, reviewer will not come to know whose paper is being reviewed and cannot identify self-citation. Reviewer only checks whether the citations given are related to that statement/ result or not. Unrelated work/ results citation is unethical. Any Journal which publishes articles with unrelated citations (self/ mutual/ others) is also considered as predatory Journal.

self-citing a document is mainly for two reasons, one, a researcher has got every reason to cite his/ her earlier works which forms the basis of one's present study, especially when the researcher is carrying forward his/ her earlier works or continues to further his/ her research findings in a chosen field. Besides, citing one's own work somewhere particularizes the research interest of a person and helps in bringing together the similar works. The negative aspect of the practice is h-index and other indices/ metrics which have somewhere become the parameter to judge the quality of a research work. Thomson Reuters resource known as Web of Science, considers "self-citation to be acceptable up to a rate of 20%, anything over that is considered suspect" (Diana Epstein, Impact factor manipulation, The Journal of the European Medical Writers Association, Vol. 16, No. 3, 2007). Citation is citation as long as it is relevant." however, in some disciplines; even 5% is too high.

In certain areas like Nanotechnology, research papers attracts more citations due to large number of researchers/ publications involved. If you have money, spend it to improve your research (speed & quality), not on publication vehicle because your publication can reach the entire world at same speed through Google Scholar without spending money by using 21st century technology-based new publication models. Actually citations should not be given so much importance to decide the quality of paper. Quality of paper and citation of paper are not directly related. Since quality is intangible, by mistake, citation is used to represent it. Citation shows continuation of research by your group or other groups. How to decide the quality of a scholarly paper is still a researchable topic. Something is better than nothing is the winners' strategy. So, ADR has applied for WOS indexing with withISSN, DOI from CrossRef, Zero APCand is available at Google Scholar. We are following ideal publication model unlike commercial model as submitted article must be reviewed for novelty, scholarly format, plagiarism, grammatical mistakes, and citation-Reference matching, etc. So kindly support us by subscription.

I was under the impression that only Scopus or SCI journals bring good citations but my publications in ADR journals brought citations from even Germany, USA, UK, and many more and helped me improve even my Google scholar h index. This happened after 2 years of my Ph.D. and also ADR journals follow zero tolerance towards plagiarism. Ultimately, research findings are made available through international platforms. Research publications in ADR follow the triple bottom lines, cost effectiveness, quality, and speed of publication. Altogether it's a unique perspective on research with focus on quality.

This discussion would help you select the best journal for your scholarly article and inspired me to offer you to submit your paper to us choosing the best Journal relevant

to the within the scope of article from our wide range of publication. Your love, hope, and belief ensure the new heights in the years to come for us along with you.

Wish you Happy New year 2022 with the hope to create an organization without any discrimination with principles of respect for difference and love for similarity in the worthy progressive journey.